

Historical Contributions of Kiswahili Language in Demonstrating Ubuntu Values in East Africa

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Abstract

The study presents the historical contributions of the Kiswahili language in demonstrating Ubuntu values in East Africa from pre-colonial times to the present. Kiswahili language represents other lingua franca that reflects Ubuntuism in the African context toward collective and holistic human development. Findings have shown that for centuries, has been a key linkage between East African communities and with outside World through its capacity to attract and accommodate other cultural diversity, It has remained a nexus of African Ubuntu expressions and conveys identity, values, inclusion, and vision of United Africa to the world. Kiswahili language remains unique as it represents African cultural values and ecology (Ubuntu) with super-diverse communities that contribute to the primary goal of alleviation of poverty through social inclusion. Kiswahili Language mediates access to key social inclusion sites such as employment, education, or health. It was further observed that Kiswahili is one of the most widely used languages of the African family, and the most widely spoken in sub-Saharan Africa. It is among the 10 most widely spoken languages in the world, with more than 200 million speakers. Apart from the historical contribution to peace-building and liberation struggles of Southern Africa and Africa in general, yet Kiswahili language is used by the new EAC to rekindle the spirit of cooperation and integration among the East African people. It is, therefore, an indispensable tool in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 and an essential factor in harmonious communication between peoples, as it promotes unity in diversity and international understanding, tolerance, and dialogue. Kiswahili helps to fight against racism, tribalism and all mother forms of injustice in Africans and it does this well because it does not raise any negative emotions amongst the users. In conclusion, the review concluded that Kiswahili continues to attract and unite millions of people all over the world with the fact that it embraces African Ubuntu values of hospitality, love, compassion, care, harmony, unity, human dignity, cooperation, and collective responsibility, etc.

Key Words: African lingua franca, Bantu language; East Africa, Kiswahili language, Swahili culture, Ubuntu philosophy,

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266

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INTRODUCTION

The study presents the historical contributions of the Kiswahili language in demonstrating Ubuntu values in East Africa from pre-colonial times to the present. Kiswahili language represents other lingua franca that reflect Ubuntuism in the African context toward collective and holistic human development (Mazrui, 1992 emphasize is mine). The study purposively selected Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda to represent other East African countries following their early exposure to the Indian coast and early contact with foreigners such as Arabs, Persians, Europeans, etc. The presence of local communities along the Indian coast played a significant contribution to the expansion of the Kiswahili language for centuries (Mazrui, 2004). The study employed the Ujamaa Intersections theory to enrich following the fact that it originates in Africa and the existing intertwined relationship with the expansion of the Kiswahili language in East Africa.

The assumptions of the Ujamaa Intersections Model are based on the existing community structures namely family, extended family, neighborhood, local leadership, ecology, spirituality, and wider attributes of the community (Lembuka, 2024c. East African communities are formed by these Ujamaa or community intersections which and their capabilities have been bounded by the Kiswahili language for centuries. The author applied the Ujamaa Intersections Model to guide the review process. Since the Ujamaa or Community Intersections Model originates from Africa, it was thought to be relevant to understanding the respective African languages (Mugumbate, 2019 & Lembuka, 2022). Ubuntu theory is grounded on the pillars of cultural values, history, and ecology that best inform and reflect the current position of the Kiswahili language as an inclusion tool of East African societies.

For this review, it is clear that Ubuntu theory can reflect a twinning historical development of Swahili culture and Kiswahili language, the Swahili name for the language itself is Kiswahili. This term is sporadically used in English as well even though the established English name for the language is Swahili (Petzell, 2012). Historically Kiswahili or Swahili language is a Bantu language that originated from the societies located along the coastal city-states of East Africa, the early contact of Arabs and Asians with Ubuntu communities in East Africa influenced the development of the Swahili language (Mpangala, 2017). The mixture of Ubuntu culture and Arab culture influenced the development of Swahili culture in East Africa from 200 AD (Mpangala, 2017).

Ubuntu communities or Bantu-speaking communities originate from the Indigenous name known as bantu, mantu, mtu, and bamutu, etc., the term bantu originated from bantu local languages of African societies (Lembuka, 2024a). Bantuism simply means African humanness or humanity where people are completely human by placing the needs of others before theirs. Also, Bantuism as a form of African Ubuntu, believes that people are not born alone but into a larger community where holistic and collective approaches are key for human development. Ubuntu culture was demonstrated by most Bantu-speaking societies in East Africa that were exposed to early socio-economic interaction with Arabs from Oman which marked the emergence of Swahili culture (Lembuka, 2022).

During the time of slave trading along the coast of East Africa, Kiswahili was spoken by slave traders and was verbally transferred and adopted by other trading posts. It was reported that during the post-slave trade period, Kiswahili became the mother tongue of some of the descendants of the freed slaves (Rwezaura, 1993). Overtime, the development of Swahili culture facilitated good positioning of the Swahili language in East African societies whereby Swahili culture is a subculture of Ubuntu culture that represents a cross-cutting cultural practice in sub-Saharan Africa which laid the foundation of Kiswahili language (Lembuka, 2024).

Ubuntu is a way of African life that has been practiced across sub-Saharan Africa from pre-colonial times to the present, Ubuntu is termed different in different African societies but it embraces similar visions and approaches toward socio-economic and political development in human faces thus Kiswahili and Ubuntu are inseparable (Mugumbate et al, 2019). African Ubuntu entails cultural values, history, and ecology toward humanness or humanity where major all aspects of human life are grounded on the values of togetherness, cooperation, interdependence, harmony, tolerance, equality, Ujamaa, utu, social justice, and inclusion, etc. (Mgumbate et al, 2013).

Apart from Arabs from Oman, Bantu-speaking societies along the East African Indian Ocean over centuries continued to interact with other foreigners particularly Portuguese cementing the development and spread of the Swahili language to the interior of East and Central Africa. Kiswahili became one of the advanced and dominant Bantu languages in along the coast of East Africa (Lewis, 2009). The Bantu languages are a subgroup of the Niger-Congo family and constitute the largest language group in Africa (Lewis, 2009). The development of Swahili culture facilitated the penetration of the Kiswahili language to Bantu and non-Bantu-speaking people across Africa (Lembuka, 2023).

Post-colonial Africa experienced various types of conflicts and chaos based on racism and tribalism, with abundant Ubuntu values Kiswahili language was able to penetrate the multicultural setting (Lembuka, 2022). Kiswahili is a functioning language that creates a friendly environment for speakers necessary to encounter culture shock in a multicultural setting. Experienced have shown that when a person is exposed to a new culture, language, and ecology may experience some changes, these changes especially language tend to cause cultural shock and since the language in use might not be the first language of the person, they might end up experiencing the so-called culture shock (Lugava et al, 2023).

According to Cupsa (2018) who defined culture shock as the anxiety and disorientation experienced when a person is made to operate in a new culture. Culture shock has been a barrier to individuals' interaction at local, regional, and international platforms where it undermines the movement of people, goods, and services Worldwide. In addressing culture shock, the Kiswahili language became an advocating tool for intercultural communication that encourages healthy communication among individuals belonging to various cultures necessary to help them adjust quickly (Petzell, 2012). Also, Kiswahili is promoting intercultural communication and strengthening national ethos amongst the co-cultures of the East African regions (Petzell, 2012).

Swahili is the largest Bantu language when it comes to the number of speakers who use it as a second or third language (and lingua franca), but the number of mother tongue speakers in the world is fairly low. There are mother-tongue speakers of Swahili in Kenya and Tanzania, but Swahili functions as a lingua franca in Burundi, Rwanda, Uganda, and the Democratic Republic of Congo as well (Lewis, 2009). Kiswahili Language is not merely a tool for communication, but the bearer of a whole nexus of African Ubuntu expressions and conveys identity, values, inclusion, and vision of United Africa. Not only Kiswahili language is characterized by unique features but most importantly it entails decolonization and inclusive aspects different from most World languages (Lembuka, 2023). Most of the East African countries are characterized by triglossia based on their former colonial masters but Kiswahili is the widespread language understood by very nearly the entire population in East Africa the position of Kiswahili language is remarkably super-passing some former colonial languages (Lugava et al, 2023).

Kiswahili language remains unique as it represents African cultural values and ecology (Ubuntu) with super-diverse communities that contribute to the primary goal of poverty alleviation and realizing sustainable development as it mediates access to key social inclusion sites such as employment, culture, education, and health, etc. (Lembuka, 2023). In line with other contributions, the Kiswahili language increased the sense of belonging and meaningful interaction from the micro to the macro level of human functioning (Piller & Takahashi 2011). Kiswahili has been useful in educational settings despite various ethnic languages in East African countries yet Kiswahili contributes as a national language and medium of instruction in social, economic, health, and political settings (Nyerere, 2011).

Sustainable development goes together with language competence in society, East African societies have been using the Kiswahili language to realize sustainable development through language competence. Since the Kiswahili language has direct connections with existing Bantu or mother languages of East Africa, for instance, governments have imposed several measures to integrate the Kiswahili language in education settings in the process of fighting against illiteracy and poverty (Nyerere, 2011). For example, in Tanzania Kiswahili proved to be more competent in an education setting as it easily attracts and links educators and learners in the education process i.e. when teachers talk to students in a language they understand, it creates meaningful interaction to their knowledge gaining and leads to sustainable learning. Unlike the use of another foreign language, the use of Swahili leads to no communication barrier for both learners and teachers (Mugaya, 2018).

Despite abundant multilingual societies in Africa, for some years, Kiswahili has been a widely spread language and used for intercultural communication, the situation has taken on a strong position in east and central African countries (Mugaya, 2018). Diverse language groups in East Africa actively engage one another through Kiswahili language as a friendly medium of communication, therefore, easing trans-border communication (Luvaga et al, 2021). This favours the use of Kiswahili language in micro, mezzo, and macro levels across multilingual and multicultural environments i.e. it is encouraging to note that the negative perspective is gradually

changing through the use of Kiswahili as a cross-cultural lingua franca in the East African region and beyond.

The fact about Kiswahili language is an inclusive communicative tool, Today Kiswahili language apart from being the official language of countries like Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda, etc. Yet Kiswahili remains to be the most common language spoken in East Africa and beyond, and it continues to be one of the most widely used languages of the African family, and the most widely spoken in sub-Saharan Africa (Yogi, 2017). It is among the 10 most widely spoken languages in the world, with more than 200 million speakers (UNESCO, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The article used the desk review method to conduct a literature review on the demonstration of the Kiswahili language as a tool of inclusion in East Africa. To complement the review, the author applied Ubuntu theory to guide the review process and since Ubuntu theory originated from Africa then the theory was thought to be relevant to understand respective African language (Mugumbate, 2019 & Lembuka, 2023). Ubuntu theory is grounded on the pillars of cultural values, history and ecology that were thought to be relevant to study Kiswahili language, the theory best inform and reflect the current position of Kiswahili language as an inclusion tool of East African societies.

Diagram 1.0: Ujamaa Intersections Theory

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CASE STUDY

As early as before the 10th century, Swahili was spoken on the East Coast of Africa and was later experienced a great influence by the emergence of coastal city-states such as Lamu, Kilwa, Malindi, Mzizima, Zanzibar, etc. (Mazrui, 1995). The name Swahili is said to originate from (the plural of) the Arabic word for 'coast': Sawahil (Petzell, 2012). It was on the islands and along the East African coast that the language arose to facilitate the communication between merchants from Asia and Early East African traders (Petzell, 2012). The language did not extend into the mainland until the 19th century, but when it did, the language spread rapidly as a result of trade in slaves, ebony, gold, and ivory (Petzell, 2012).

During the time of slave trading along the coast of East Africa, in Tanganyika and Zanzibar, Kiswahili was spoken by slave traders and was verbally transferred and adopted by other trading posts. During the post-slave trade period, Kiswahili became the mother tongue of some of the descendants of the freed slaves as well as Zanzibar (Rwezaura, 1993). During the exertion of colonial power and dominance, the German colonial interest began in the 1880s and by that time, the Swahili language was already widespread (Yogi, 2017). The German colonists encouraged a further spread of the Kiswahili language in German East Africa since they depended on it for their administration. Even though German was taught as a subject in school, Swahili was the medium of instruction and the Germans documented the language (Petzell, 2012).

During the independence struggle in East Africa was used as a tool of identity and unification, taking a good example of Kenya's African National Union (KANU) and Tanganyika's African National Union (TANU) (Nyerere, 2011). In the 1950s, the historical contributions of Tanzania formerly known as Tanganyika in the development of the Kiswahili language can't be undermined since the status of Swahili was further strengthened in political activities when TANU (Tanganyika African National Union) was formed in 1954 and began using the language to mobilize the people in the struggle for independence. Since such a large number of people already understood the language, it came to be a unifying force. Politicians had hardly any need for interpreters because Swahili was understood all over the country (Rubagumya, 1990).

The former president Dr. Julius Nyerere contributed greatly to the consolidation of Swahili. Being a teacher of both English and Swahili, he translated (and published) Shakespeare's Julius Caesar into Swahili himself (Nyerere, 2011). He proclaimed the use of the language and it was during his leadership that Tanzania became the first country in Africa to make an African language the national one. When Swahili was declared the national language in 1964, several institutes and organizations were established to coordinate and maintain the language. Overall direction and coordination of these activities was the responsibility of the Promoter of Swahili including the late Dr. Julius Kambarage Nyerere (Ubuntu PhD) (Bamgbose, 1999). As mentioned, the new words that are taken into the Swahili language come from English. That is the reverse of what former president Dr. Nyerere stated in 1978; namely that new words should, if possible, come from other Tanzanian Bantu languages before foreign languages were considered (Legère, 2002).

Today, Kiswahili is the most common language spoken in East Africa taking practical examples of Tanzania, Uganda, and Kenya, and it continues to be one of the most widely used languages of the African family, and the most widely spoken in sub-Saharan Africa (Yogi, 2017). Moreover, the Kiswahili language has been a significant tool in the new East African Community to rekindle the spirit of cooperation toward regional integration among the East African people.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pre-colonial traditional communities in East Africa were typical Ubuntu communities connected with collective and holistic traditional approaches in utilizing ecology through carrying out various socio-economic activities aimed at improving their living conditions and mastering their socio-environment (Lembuka, 2023). Evidence has shown that the evolution of man and human societies existed in pre-historic Tanganyika which made it possible for the development of these traditional communities into advanced cultural practices and a common language (Mpangala, 2010). Various scholars have termed existing Ubuntu communities as Bantu-speaking people based on inclusive language practice across East African societies, common language was one of the core aspects of Ubuntu practice where communities were organized and connected to the ecology.

Depending on the geographical location, people were identified and united with the unique traditional language practice of Ubuntu through communal ownership of resources, cooperation, humanity, mutual support, etc. (Mpangala, 2017). The practice of Ubuntu culture in East Africa under Bantu-speaking communities in East Africa like other African communities holds the ideal of a common language that connects Africans and holistic ecology. The Bantu idea of *Ubuntu* sees humans as connected through inclusive and holistic language towards threads in a web, or bricks in a building living peacefully and interdependence in a community (Thomson, 2022). The position of an individual in these Bantu-speaking communities is directly connected with the community based on the African culture and similar language, therefore common language will always be part of the community (Lembuka, 2023).

Ubuntu culture can be termed as a traditional or Indigenous practice that existed from pre-colonial times to presents with values of compassion, togetherness, cooperation, care, social justice, interdependence, equality, hospitality, *utu*, and *Ujamaa*, etc. (Mpangala, 2010). The practice of Ubuntu culture in East African communities differs in terms of localities, economic activities and nature of socio-economic organization but they have similar cultural values and language perspectives (Lembuka, 2023). In the course of mastering their environment and developing human welfare, Africans formed various traditional communities that shared common values, ecology, and language. Also, the traditional African communities were bonded by Ubuntu ideology and practice that embraced existing cultural values, ecology, and common language with a central focus on respect for human dignity (Mugumbate 2013).

The collective and holistic capacity of the Kiswahili language can be traced back to the pre-colonial times through reflections of traditional communities in East Africa that were typical Ubuntu communities, these Ubuntu communities or Bantu-speaking communities were connected

with common language practice known as the Bantu language. Ubuntu is a general culture that produced other subcultures that embrace similar values and vision across Africa with collective and holistic approaches in utilizing ecology through carrying out various socio-economic activities aimed at improving their living conditions and mastering their socio-environment (Lembuka, 2023).

Post-colonial Africa experienced various types of conflicts and chaos based on racism and tribalism, with abundant Ubuntu values Kiswahili language was able to penetrate the multicultural setting (Lembuka, 2023). Kiswahili is a functioning language that creates a friendly environment for the speaker necessary to encounter culture shock in a multicultural setting. Experienced have shown that when a person is exposed to a new culture, language, and ecology may experience some changes, these changes especially language tend to cause cultural shock and since the language in use might not be the first language of the person, they might end up experiencing the so-called culture shock (Lugava et al, 2023).

Despite of existence of various lingua francs in Africa, the Kiswahili language holds the capacity to embrace cultural diversity that exists within more than 200 ethnic tribes of East African societies. According to Cupsa (2018) who defined culture shock as the anxiety and disorientation experienced when a person is made to operate in a new culture. Culture shock has been a barrier to individuals' interaction at local, regional, and international platforms where it undermines the movement of people, goods, and services Worldwide. In addressing culture shock, the Kiswahili language became an advocating tool for intercultural communication that encourages healthy communication among individuals belonging to various cultures necessary to help them adjust quickly (Petzell, 2012). Also, Kiswahili is promoting intercultural communication and strengthening national ethos amongst the co-cultures of the East African regions (Petzell, 2012).

With no hidden agenda like colonial domination or exclusion of some people, the Kiswahili language is grounded in human dignity rather than colonial legacy. Inclusiveness of the Kiswahili language positions it as the largest Bantu language when it comes to the number of speakers who use it as a second or third language (and lingua franca), but the number of mother tongue speakers in the world is fairly low. There are mother-tongue speakers of Swahili in Kenya and Tanzania, but Swahili functions as a lingua franca in Burundi, Rwanda, Uganda, and the Democratic Republic of Congo as well (Lewis, 2009). Kiswahili Language is not merely a tool for communication, but the bearer of a whole nexus of African Ubuntu expressions and conveys identity, values, inclusion, and vision of United Africa. Not only Kiswahili language is characterized by unique features but most importantly it entails decolonization and inclusive aspects different from most World languages (Lembuka, 2023).

Most of the East African countries are characterized by triglossia based on their former colonial masters but Kiswahili is the widespread language understood by very nearly the entire population in East Africa but the position of Kiswahili language is remarkably super passing some former colonial languages (Lugava et al, 2023). Kiswahili language remains unique as it represents African cultural values and ecology (Ubuntu) with super-diverse communities that contribute to

the primary goal of poverty alleviation and realizing sustainable development as it mediates access to key social inclusion sites such as employment, culture, education, and health, etc. (Lembuka, 2023). In line with other contributions, the Kiswahili language increased the sense of belonging and meaningful interaction from the micro to the macro level of human functioning (Piller & Takahashi 2011).

Kiswahili has been useful in educational settings despite various ethnic languages in East African countries yet Kiswahili contributes as a national language and medium of instruction in social, economic, health, and political settings (Nyerere, 2011). Realization of sustainable development goes together with language competence in the society, East African societies have been using the Kiswahili language to realize sustainable development through language competence. Since the Kiswahili language has direct connections with existing Bantu or mother languages of East Africa, for instance, governments have imposed several measures to integrate the Kiswahili language in education settings in the process of fighting against illiteracy and poverty (Nyerere, 2011). For example, in Tanzania, the realization of the Universal Education Policy was demonstrated through the Kiswahili language as it created meaningful interaction among education instructors and learners (Mugaya, 2018).

Despite abundant multilingual societies in Africa, for some years, Kiswahili has been a widely spread language and used for intercultural communication, the situation has taken on a strong position in east and central African countries (Mugaya, 2018). Diverse language groups in East Africa actively engage one another through Kiswahili language as a friendly medium of communication, therefore, easing trans-border communication (Luvaga et al, 2021). This favours the use of Kiswahili language in micro, mezzo, and macro levels across multilingual and multicultural environments i.e. it is encouraging to note that the negative perspective is gradually changing through the use of Kiswahili as a cross-cultural lingua franca in the East African region and beyond. Kiswahili has made the establishment and advancement of East African regional integration and evidence has shown that the use of the Kiswahili language in EAC integration has worked well through trade, marketing, and media (Ramadhan, 2020).

Kiswahili language became a communicative tool that united East African people and facilitated easy communication across the countries, communication is a key factor in every development project that involves people, and regional integration involves people from different cultures with different languages but all are connected through Kiswahili language (Ramadhan, 2020). Being a principal component of African culture, the Kiswahili language continued to be the greatest mediator that allows people to relate to and understand each other in this multicultural environment (Ramadhan, 2020). To compete successfully in today's multicultural environment, Kiswahili overcame the communication inadequacies resulting from differences in languages and varied cultures within East Africa (Aruna & Badi, 2006).

Kiswahili is one of the most widely used languages of the African family, and the most widely spoken in sub-Saharan Africa. It is among the 10 most widely spoken languages in the world, with more than 200 million speakers (UNESCO, 2021). Apart from the historical contribution in peace-

building and liberation struggles of Southern Africa and Africa in general (SADC, 2019), yet Kiswahili language is used by the new EAC to rekindle the spirit of cooperation and integration among the East African people. It is, therefore, an indispensable tool in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 and an essential factor in harmonious communication between peoples, as it promotes unity in diversity and international understanding, tolerance and dialogue.

Kiswahili language remains unique as it represents African cultural values and ecology (Ubuntu) with super-diverse communities that contribute to the primary goal of alleviation of poverty through social inclusion. Kiswahili Language mediates access to key social inclusion sites such as employment, education, or health. Second, a sense of belonging is negotiated through language and often tied to specific competencies (Piller & Takahashi 2011). By using a common language, a community of Kiswahili speakers is created, binding all other language groups together. The binding mechanism should not be mistaken for assimilation; individuals from diverse language groups are free to alternate between their native cultures and the Kiswahili culture. Nevertheless, the fact that diversity still predominates individualistic culture, the various communities are obliged to interact to co-exist through a cross-border call to fulfil the demands of social life under the common language of Kiswahili (Luvaga et al, 2021).

Non-colonial and domination features of the Kiswahili language have positioned it in different societies and nations throughout history, it also mediates the goal for a mutual adaptation that results in biculturalism instead of assimilation, to boost the development of intercultural sensitivity to both the individuals and organizations, supporting empathic understanding and coordination of activities across different cultures (Lewis, 2009). According to Luvaga et al (2021) by using Kiswahili as a common language, a community of Kiswahili speakers was created and bonded all other groups together. The binding mechanism of the Kiswahili language should not be mistaken for assimilation and related colonial domination since individuals from diverse language groups are free to alternate between their native cultures and the Kiswahili culture.

In an educational setting, the Kiswahili language considers, attracts, and accommodates learners collectively and holistically in the learning process at various levels of education setting. Since both educators and learners are familiar with the Kiswahili language then it becomes when teachers talk to students in a language they understand, it creates meaningful interaction in their knowledge-gaining and leads to sustainable learning (Mugaya, 2018). However, due to prevailing multilingual societies, the need for a useful language of instruction could be the base for communication in classroom interaction. For some years, Kiswahili has been a widely spread language and used for intercultural communication, the situation has taken on a strong position in East and Central African countries. This favours the use of the Kiswahili language in education (Mugaya, 2018).

Wright (2000) clearly shows how language is often a critical thinker of national development and regional integration, especially in developing countries. There are different theories as to why Swahili is found to be more acceptable or neutral to other tribes, putting aside the fact that it originated from the East African coast of the Indian Ocean. One of the most common theories that

most people have been told is that Kiswahili does not belong to anyone or any tribe (Wright, 2000). This means that Kenyans, Burundians, South Sudanese, Rwandans, Tanzanians, Somalis, Ugandans, and the rest of East Africa embrace this language as they believe it is not biased against their languages. Of course, history would show that Kiswahili's neutrality is debatable depending on who you ask because if it were to be claimed then those from the East African coast could claim its ownership. It is an incontrovertible fact that Kiswahili has helped with cohesion when it involves peace and stability within the East African region (Wright, 2000).

It was further noted that without the Kiswahili language, Kenya and Tanzania would be in chaos, which would heavily affect the rest of East Africa because these two countries are dependent on when it comes to trade and reference to the surface world, especially Kenya. Tanzania may be a great example of how a rustic with quite 120 tribes has been ready to maintain peace and stability. The country enjoys peace and stability because of using Kiswahili and not focusing as much on other languages or tribes, especially the ones with a majority of political leaders (Ramadhan, 2020). No doubt that the application of the theory of Ubuntu in this review brought a theoretical explanation theoretically of how the Kiswahili language reflects its inclusive roles in East Africa in various settings.

Embracement and demonstration of Ubuntu values are vital for East African people from micro, mezzo, and macro levels of human functioning within various social structures and shared vision on social, political, military, and economic agenda (Lembuka, 2023b). Ujamaa Intersections theory best guides the opportunities that Kiswahili language can be applied by various policymakers and other key stakeholders in realizing unity, regional integration, and sustainable development in the East African region and beyond. Moreover, it is clear that Kiswahili as a common language identifies and unites East African people regardless of their geographical locations from local to international platforms (Ramadhan, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The compatibility of Ujamaa Intersections Theory and the Kiswahili language provided a relevant analysis and presentation of the capabilities of African Ubuntu values, the theory provided relevant holistic reflections of both Swahili culture and Kiswahili language. Embracement of African Ubuntu culture in Swahili culture influenced the Kiswahili language to fight against racism, tribalism, discrimination and all mother forms of injustice in the East African region and it does this well because it does not raise any negative emotions, exclusion, and classes amongst the Kiswahili speakers. Kiswahili language successfully penetrated today's challenging multicultural environment and overcame the communication inadequacies resulting from differences in languages and varied cultures by promoting intercultural communication and strengthening national ethos amongst the co-cultures of the East African regions

Also, the existing remarkable position of Kiswahili in maintaining identity and promoting unity encourages understanding through human interaction between the dominant and the co-cultures in

East Africa and outside. Lastly, the Kiswahili language will continue to attract and unite millions of people all over the world with the fact that it embraces African Ubuntu values including love, compassion, care, harmony, humanity, hospitality, unity, cooperation collective responsibility, etc. Apart from the historical contribution to peace-building and liberation struggles of Southern Africa and Africa in general, yet Kiswahili language is used by the new East African Community to rekindle the spirit of cooperation and regional integration among the East African people. Therefore it is recommended for the full utilization of the Kiswahili language as the soft tool relevant in achieving the goals of the New East African Community and the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030.

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REFERENCE

Badi, R. V. and Aruna, K. (2006). *Business Communication (Second Edition)*: New Delhi, India: Vrinda Publications (P) Ltd

Behning, A. (2017). *Intercultural Communication: An Overview*. WITOS Berlin.

Bennett, J. M. (2018). *Intercultural Communication (Extended Encyclopaedia Entries in Multicultural America: A multimedia encyclopaedia)*. Accessed from <https://www.idrinstitute.org/resources/intercultural-communication/>.

Cupsa, I. (2018). Culture shock and identity. *Transactional Analysis Journal*, 48(2), 181-191.

Lembuka, M. (2024a). *The Evolution of Community Development thorough Ubuntu Perspective in Tanzania*. *East African Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 219-231. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajass.7.1.1870>

Lembuka, H.M. (2024b). *Analysis of Villagization Model of Rural Community Development in Tanzania Mainland Through Ubuntu Lens* <https://www.infoagepub.com/products/Community-Development-Practice-in-Africa>

Lembuka, H.M. (2022). *The prominence of Mwalimu Julius K. Nyerere in The History of Community Development in Tanzania – Ubuntu Perspective*: <https://ticd.ac.tz/wpcontent/uploads/2023/11/4.-Meinrad-Copy.pdf>

Lewis, M. P., (ed.) (2009), "Ethnologue: Languages of the World, Sixteenth edition." Retrieved 20 September 2011, from <http://www.ethnologue.com/>.

Mazrui A.A. & Mazrui A. (1995). *Swahili State and Society*. Nairobi: East African Educational Publishers.

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277

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- Mazrui, A.A. (1992). Roots of Kiswahili: Colonialism, Nationalism, and the Dual Heritage. *Ufahamu*, 20, 88-100.
- Mpangala, G.P. (2017). The African Renaissance and Struggles for the Third Phase of Nation-Building in Africa: The Experience of Tanzania. *Tanzania Zamani: A Journal of Historical Research and Writing*. <https://journals.udsm.ac.tz/index.php/tz/article/view/1674>
- Mugaya S.T. (2018). The use of Kiswahili Language and Learning Approaches in Classroom Interaction: A Case Study of Secondary Schools in Dodoma, Tanzania
- Mugumbate, J. & Chereni, A. (2019). Using African Ubuntu theory in social work with children in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Social Work*, 9.
- Mugumbate, J. & Nyanguru, A. (2013). Exploring African philosophy: The value of Ubuntu in social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 3:82-100.
- Mugaya S.T (2018). The use of Kiswahili Language and Learning Approaches in Classroom Interaction: A Case Study of Secondary Schools in Dodoma, Tanzania
- Mugumbate, J. & Chereni, A. (2019). Using African Ubuntu theory in social work with children in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Social Work*, 9.
- Mugumbate, J. & Nyanguru, A. (2013). Exploring African philosophy: The value of Ubuntu in social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 3:82-100.
- Persikova, T.N. (2004). *Intercultural Communication and Corporate Culture: Textbook manual for schools/ TN Persikov*. - Moscow: Logos, 2004. - 224 p.
- Petzell, M. (2008). *The Kagulu language of Tanzania: grammar, texts and vocabulary*. Cologne: Rüdiger Köppe Verlag.
- Petzell, M. (2012). *The linguistic situation in Tanzania*, University of Gothenburg
- Ramadhan, P.W. (2020). *The Influence of Language on Regional Integration: Case Study – Kiswahili Language and East African Community*
- Rubagumya, C. M. (1990), "Introduction", in Rubagumya, C. M. (ed.), *Language in education in Africa: a Tanzanian perspective*. Clevedon (UK): Multilingual Matters Inc. 57, 1-4.
- Rubagumya, C. M. (1990), "Language in Tanzania", in Rubagumya, C. M. (ed.), *Language in education in Africa: a Tanzanian perspective*. Clevedon (UK): Multilingual Matters Inc, 5-14.
- Wright, S. (2000). *Community and Communication: The Role of Language in Nation State Building and European Integration*.